

Kinetic Study of Hydrolysis of Sucrose catalysed by Invertase in Aquo-polyhydric Alcohols

J. SUNITHA and P. K. SAIPRAKASH*

Department of Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007

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Dastol and Price first observed enzymatic activities of crystalline chymotrypsin and xanthine oxidase in anhydrous non-polar organic solvents¹. Since then several enzymatic transformations in non-polar organic solvents have been reported². Recently, Zaks and Kilbanov³ have listed several potential advantages of employing biocatalysts in organic media as opposed to water. To the applied enzymologist it is not uncommon for catalytic rate enhancement of several billion fold to be observed in non-aqueous solvents⁴. Many enzymes have been shown to be catalytically active in a wide variety of organic solvents⁵. However, selection of suitable solvent is difficult as they can also inactivate the enzymes⁶. Criteria that should be taken into consideration in the selection of organic solvent for enzyme catalysis include solubility of reactants, activity and stability of enzymes, toxicity and inflammability⁷.

Since the purpose of majority of studies is to increase the yields of products, it can be done by addition of organic cosolvent to the existing aqueous media. In the present study a comparison of activity of invertase in aqueous and aquo-polyolic media is attempted by selecting four structurally similar polyhydric alcohols. The polyhydric alcohols were investigated since invertase is thermodynamically stable, catalytically active and sucrose is readily soluble in these solvents. In addition, polyhydric alcohols are non-toxic, non-flammable, easy to handle and biologically important.

Results and Discussion

The influence of different polyhydric alcohols containing two to six carbon atoms and hydroxyl

groups, viz. ethylene glycol (C₂), glycerol (C₃), erythritol (C₄) and sorbitol (C₆) on the activity of invertase has been studied. It was observed (Table 1) that the activity of invertase gradually increased with the increase in the carbon chain length of polyols compared to that in aqueous media. At fixed concentration (0.2 M) of polyols, the increased rates in ethylene glycol, glycerol, erythritol and sorbitol media were found to be 14, 28, 35 and 47% respectively more than that of aqueous medium (Table 1). As there is steady increase in the reaction velocity one can correlate the increase in number of hydroxyl groups of polyols with the reaction rates. This enhanced activity in non-aqueous solvent is due to the presence of organic solvent around the micro-environment of the enzyme that can alter the secondary, tertiary and quaternary structures of the protein and can penetrate into the active sites of the enzyme and disrupt the chemical and structural balance and thereby promoting higher activity of the enzyme⁸. Invertase in 100% polyhydric alcoholic media shows no activity at all which indicates that removal of water from microenvironment of enzyme, drastically distorts the enzyme conformations and inactivates the enzyme (Table 2). Therefore, some degree of hydration of the invertase is necessary to maintain the catalytic activity⁹. Low concentration of polyols enhances activity, which may be due to the restoration of condition more closely resembling those in cellular environment in which these enzymes are presumably optimal¹⁰.

The optimum pH of invertase is 4.5 and there is no alteration in pH optima when invertase is dissolved in different polyols. Although slight broadening in pH curves were observed which in-

creased with the increase in chain length of the polyols. Hence the enzyme can be employed at a wider pH range when it is dissolved in polyols.

TABLE 1—ACTIVITY OF INVERTASE (AMOUNT OF SUCROSE HYDROLYSED PER MIN) COMPARED IN AQUEOUS AND AQUO-POLYOLIC MEDIA AT 333 K IN 0.2M POLYOLS AT pH 4.5

Medium	Activity mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	Activity %
Aqueous media	0.051	100
Aquo-ethylene glycol	0.058	114
Aquo-glycerol	0.064	128
Aquo-erythritol	0.068	135
Aquo-sorbitol	0.074	147

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF DIFFERENT POLYOLS ON ACTIVITY OF INVERTASE AT 333 K AND AT pH 4.5

Concn. of polyols mol dm ⁻³	Activity (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹)			
	Ethylene glycol	Glycerol	Erythritol	Sorbitol
0.025	0.050	0.054	0.055	0.059
0.050	0.056	0.058	0.058	0.062
0.100	0.063	0.066	0.069	0.078
3.000	0.048	0.042	0.041	0.038
4.000	0.041	0.038	0.031	0.031
5.000	0.033	0.028	0.027	0.023
100%	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

The optimum temperature of invertase at 0.1 M acetate buffer of pH. 4.5 is 55° and there is no shift in optimum temperature when invertase is dissolved in different polyols. The change in water content affects not only the activity but also the stability. Invertase in aqueous media was denatured at 65° only. But when incubated in polyols, it showed tremendous increase in thermal stability. Thermal stability increased with the carbon chain length of polyol molecule and also with the increase in polyol concentration. This unusual stability of invertase in polyhydric alcohols is due to the three-dimensional conformation of enzyme, which is stabilised by low energy bonds that are broken mainly as a result of an increase in vibration energy and collision with water molecules as temperature is raised. As the energy caused by water, protein hydrogen bonds is of the same magnitude as that of the enzyme intramolecular bonds, compounds having low interaction with the enzyme but interacting strongly with water will stabilise the enzyme¹¹. Invertase is more stable in polyols because hydrogen bond forming solvents like polyols have greater affinity for water.

Substrate inhibition : The apparent activity of invertase declines in sucrose solutions of concentration above 0.3 M. This phenomenon is generally attributed to the inhibition by excess of substrate and the solute-solvent interactions in the aqueous solution of sucrose which are due to a modification of the conformation of sucrose. In fact when the sucrose concentration increases, the decrease in water activity results in modification of the distribution of hydrogen bonds¹². Intermolecular hydrogen bonds of sucrose are replaced by intramolecular ones. This gives a folded and aggregated structure for sucrose molecule which may finally yield the sucrose crystal structure that are not recognised by the invertase¹³. Substrate inhibition decreases with increase in the number of hydroxyl groups of polyols. This is due to sucrose molecule undergoing a conformational change with the establishment of intermolecular hydrogen bonding between the hydroxyl groups of the polyols and water. With the increase in number of hydroxyl groups there is a chance of formation of more hydrogen bonds resulting in the reduction of substrate inhibition. With the increase in concentration of polyols from 2.0 to 4.0 M, substrate inhibition increases due to the establishment of intramolecular hydrogen bonds between polyol molecules.

Kinetic and thermodynamic parameters : Lineweaver-Burk plots of 1/V vs 1/[S] were drawn (Figs. 1 and 2) at temperatures 30, 40 and 50°. The K_m and V_{max} values in aquo-polyolic media were compared to that in aqueous medium. There is a regular

Fig. 1. Lineweaver-Burk plots in aqueous media at pH 4.5 and at (A) 30°, (B) 40° and (C) 50°.

Fig. 2. Plots of $1/V$ vs $1/[S]$ in $0.02 M$ sorbitol at (A) 30° , (B) 40° and (C) 50° .

trend in decrease in K_m values with the increases in the molecular weight of the polyols (Table 3). This is due to the changes in solvent properties from water to polyols which decreases the solvent dielectric constant and causes significant decrease in water content of the medium. These changes effect enzymatic catalysis as catalytic efficiency of an enzyme depends on the ability of enzyme to utilise the free energy of binding with the substrate. This binding energy reflects the difference between binding energies of substrate-enzyme and substrate-solvent interactions¹⁴. Kinetic parameters describing enzyme functions, such as binding constant with substrate (K), Michaelis-Menten constant (K_m) and catalytic turnover (v_{max}) therefore depend strongly upon the reaction medium.

TABLE 3—KINETIC PARAMETERS OF INVERTASE IN AQUEOUS AND $0.2 M$ OF POLYOLS AT $313 K$ AT pH 4.5

Medium	$10^3 K_m$ mol dm ⁻³	v_{max} mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	$10^5 k$ min ⁻¹
Aqueous	7.828	0.0515	7.080
Ethylene glycol	6.671	0.0538	7.392
Glycerol	5.978	0.0610	8.383
Erythritol	5.001	0.0625	8.592
Sorbitol	3.886	0.0694	9.547

Thermodynamic parameters of invertase in aqueous and aquo-polyolic media were calculated from Arrhenius plots. It was found that with increase in the carbon chain of polyols, activation energy and enthalpy gradually decrease (Table 4). It was observed that with the increase in the polyol con-

centration above $0.2 M$ there is a gradual decrease in the hydrolysis rates. An attempt was made to quantitatively determine the inhibition of polyols at high concentrations of polyols at 30° . It was found that there was change in slopes and intercepts with the change in concentration of polyols but K_m remains constant, so noncompetitive inhibition is said to be operative at this higher concentration.

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS IN BOTH AQUEOUS AND $0.2 M$ POLYOLS AT pH 4.5

Media	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Aqueous	12.214	11.592	84.57	-233
Ethylene glycol	9.580	8.958	84.48	-241
Glycerol	8.526	7.904	84.13	-243
Erythritol	7.663	7.041	84.06	-246
Sorbitol	5.269	4.647	83.80	-253

Experimental

The activity of invertase was assayed by modified Lane and Eynon method¹⁵ which involved estimation of the amount of sucrose hydrolysed. The reaction was initiated by adding enzyme solution prepared in $0.1 M$ acetate buffer of pH 4.5 to $0.01 M$ sucrose solutions and incubated at 55° for 5 min and was terminated by adding Fehling A and B mixture (2 ml). Then the aliquots were placed in a hot water-bath for 30 min for the complete reduction of Cu^{2+} . The absorbance of supernatant liquid was noted at 674 nm against the reagent blank and the amount of sucrose hydrolysed was estimated. 1 mg of invertase hydrolysed $1.0 \mu\text{mole}$ of sucrose per min at pH 4.5 and 55° .

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